

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF GLULAM-CFRP COMPOSITE BEAMS BASED ON BRAZILIAN RAW MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The performance of engineered timber such as fibre-reinforced (FRP) glued laminated timber, depends on the bonding quality of the elements in different configurations. The interaction between the timber and the FRP is influenced by variables such as environmental conditions, timber moisture content, timber surface treatment, adhesive mixture, and adhesive curing. The aim of this study was to analyse the bonding resistance of glulam-CFRP interface. This aim was satisfied through an experimental campaign based on both shear and flexural tests on CFRP-Glulam beams glued with a two-component polyurethane adhesive based on castor beans. As a result, shear fracture in the timber, indicating efficiency of the polyurethane adhesive.

KEYWORDS

Engineered timber; carbon fibre; adherence; experimental investigation.

INTRODUCTION

The tendency of the forestry industry to harvest plantations with shorter life cycles has led to dimensional limitations of sawn timber elements for construction. Additionally, young timber is consistently associated with the presence of defects and low quality compared to mature timber or hardwood timber sourced from native Brazilian forests. The elevated cost of native hardwood timber and the environmental controversy surrounding the harvesting of native forests results in reduced utilisation of timber in the construction sector. In this scenario, glued laminated timber (glulam) emerges as a viable alternative for the rational use of the timber since it enables the utilisation of young timber (below 20 years-old) from fast-growing species forests (Nadir et al., 2016).

In Brazil, *Eucalyptus spp.* species stands out as the most productive forests due to its capacity to adapt to a wide variety of environments, followed by the *Pinus spp.* Species, which are thrive in the southern region of Brazil. The restriction of *Pinus spp.* timber in certain regions of Brazil due to cost competitiveness turns *Eucalyptus spp.* timber more favourable option for utilisation. Undesired properties of young eucalypt timber such as juvenile portion and knots can be overcome by the lamination of the timber to lamellas and applying fibre-reinforced polymers (FRP) as reinforcing material. The reinforcement mitigates the reduced load capacity and poor lamination bonding caused by the defects of juvenile timber (Raftery; Rodd, 2015).

The performance of glulam is associated with the bonding quality of the elements in different configurations. Various adhesive made from different raw materials can be found in the market. Some popular adhesive systems are based on melamineurea formaldehyde (MUF), melamine formaldehyde (MF), phenol-resorcinol-formaldehyde (PRF), polyurethanes, and emulsion polymer isocyanate (EPI) resins (Hänsel et al., 2021). According to Balmori, Branco and Basterra (2021), the bond strength is limited by the strength of the timber itself which means that the ideal failure would occur in the timber fibres instead of the FRP.

The application of fibre-reinforced polymers (FRP) to glulam becomes important because the mechanical performance of this material is associated with several factors, such as timber species, thickness and position of the lamellae, type of adhesive and surface treatment (Calil Neto et al., 2014). Vahedian, Shrestha and Crews (2019) state that the interaction between timber and FRP is relatively complex and is influenced by several variables, such as environmental conditions, timber moisture content, surface treatment, adhesive mixture, and drying and/or curing.

Raftery and Rodd (2015) explain that epoxy adhesives are widely considered as the first choice of adhesive for timber-FRP composites. However, using a single adhesive for the entire depth of the cross-section in glulam products is significantly more economical. In other words, inspired by the effort to reduce costs of glulam beams, this study proposes gluing both timber-timber and timber-FRP with the same adhesive.

Brunetti et al. (2019) state that the possibility of using the same adhesives for gluing timber and the FRP would allow new perspectives in the use of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) in timber elements. In this context, polyurethanes are very interesting as they are widely used in the timber industry to produce glulam elements. The study developed by Sviták and Ruman (2017) showed that such adhesives could be effectively used for CFRP-glulam composite beams.

After presenting this viewpoint, this work studied the bond strength of timber-CFRP interface for glulam produced with fast-growing timber of *Eucalyptus urophylla* clone (COP 1404). A two-component polyurethane adhesive based on castor beans was used to glue the timber-timber elements and also the CFRP.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty-six logs of the clonal species of *Eucalyptus urophylla* COP 1404 were obtained from a plantation in northeast Brazil. The logs aged between 7 to 10 years-old and had an average diameter at the breast height of 12 cm at the top-end and 15 cm at the base-end. They measured approximately 3.50 meters in length. The logs were sawn in the laboratory's carpentry to lumber with a cross section width of 5 cm and a thickness of 2 or 3 cm.

A two-component adhesive was obtained from Kehl Indústria e Comércio Ltda. The polyurethane component was an MDI-type polymeric isocyanate (IC 200 - Component A), and the binder component was a bio-polyol based on castor bean oil (KDG1909 - Component B). Both the timber-timber and timber-CFRP glue lines utilized this adhesive. The CFRP used was a bidirectional fabric (CC-0202), manufactured by Fibertex, with a 2x2-twill pattern, an apparent density of 206 g/m², a weft/warp direction of 90°, and a width of 1.27 m. Pamar et al. (2015) reported a tensile strength value of 365.3 N/mm² and a tensile load capacity value of 6950 N for the bidirectional CFRP fabric. In terms of bending resistance, the maximum bending capacity value was 12.23 N/mm², and the bending capacity for the 3-point bending test was 358.05 N/mm².

Physical properties of the timber

The physical properties of the timber were determined by the apparent density and dimensional stability. The tests were carried out according to ABNT NBR 7190-3 (2022).

Glulam-CFRP composites

Two-lamellae glulam beams were produced, the lamellae were 2 cm and 3 cm thick, hence the glulam cross-section was 5 cm by 5 cm. This configuration was chosen due to the dimensions of the specimen for the shear parallel to the fibres test defined in NBR 7190-3 (ABNT, 2022), a fact justified by the alignment with the objective of this research. Two types of glulam beams were made: glulam without carbon fibre reinforcement (LSFC) and glulam with carbon fibre reinforcement (LCFC). This test was carried in 12 samples for each variable (LSFC and LCFC).

Glulam-CFRP fabrication procedure

The fabrication of the glulam beam considered the moisture content (MC) and the adhesive proportion. The lamellae were at MC = 15%, and the adhesive quantity was 225 g/m². To measure the moisture content of each lamella, the DUC 2050 Digisystem contact moisture meter model was utilised. The mixture ratio was equal to 2:1 (component B to component A). The adhesive was applied on two sides of the lamella. The bonding pressure was 0.7 MPa with a pressing time of 18 hours, and curing period of at least 8 days.

The glulam-CFRP fabrication procedure is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Fabrication process of the Glulam-CFRP beams

After gluing the CFRP in the lamella, the second lamella was pressed using a press with four pressure application points using a torque wrench, whose torque was 88.2 N.m, to produce a pressure of 0.7 MPa. Figure 2 illustrates the process.

Figure 2: Pressing process of the lamella to produce the glulam beam

After the pressing time, the beams were adjusted on the table saw. Then, the specimens referring to each test were cut. First, an investigation was carried out about the bond strength of the timber fibre. This verification was carried out through shear parallel to the grain tests, comparing the shear strength of glued laminated wood without CFRP (LSFC) and glued laminated wood with CFRP (LCFC).

Shear parallel to the grain at the glue line test

The shear parallel to the grain at the glue line test followed the guidelines of NBR 7190-3 (ABNT, 2022), carried out according to the same shear test procedure for solid timber, with specimens of the same dimensions indicated in that standard. Figure 3 shows the configuration of the specimen.

a) Specimen without CFRP (LSFC) b) Specimen with CFRP (LCFC)

Figure 3: Specimen for shear parallel to the grain at the glue line test

Four-point bending test

This test followed the procedures specified in the Brazilian standard ABNT NBR 7190-4 (2022), employing a span ratio of $18h$ and loading applied at two points. The specimens featured a rectangular cross-section measuring $4\text{ cm} \times 4\text{ cm}$, spanning 72 cm . Figure 4 illustrates the configuration of the specimen. The laminated composite consisted of two lamellae of equal thickness, encompassing two lamellae with 2 cm thick. The modulus of elasticity (MOE or E_0) was determined by assessing the vertical displacement at the central point of the lower surface of the beam in relation to the supporting elements.

Figure 4: Specimen for four-point bending test

Shear test parallel to the grain

The shear test parallel to the fibres was carried in accordance with ABNT NBR 7190-4 (2022), whose test configuration and specimen is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Specimen for shear parallel to the grain test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical properties of the timber

The *Eucalyptus* COP 1404 timber has basic density of 465 kg/m³, longitudinal shrinkage of 0.3%, radial shrinkage of 4.6%, and tangential shrinkage of 5.6%, with a coefficient of anisotropy equals to 1.2. According to Serpa and Vital (2005), values of coefficient of anisotropy lower than 1.5 indicates a stable timber for sawing. The average basic density values fell within the range reported by Silva (2018), and closely resembled the basic density identified for clone COP 1404 in the investigation conducted by Paulino and Lima (2018), amounting to 470 kg/m³.

Furthermore, the density closely corresponds to the densities observed in species commonly utilized for glulam production, around 465 kg/m³. For instance, Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) has a basic density of 476 kg/m³ (Andor et al., 2015), while Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*) exhibits a basic density of approximately 480 kg/m³ (Ling et al., 2018). Likewise, *Pinus sylvestris* showcases a basic density of 475 kg/m³, and fast-growing poplar demonstrates a density of 325 kg/m³ (Wang et al., 2021).

As noted by Oliveira, Hellmeister, and Tomazello Filho (2005), young trees typically have reduced densities in comparison to mature trees. This lower density profile favours the penetration of adhesives into the timber surface, thereby enhancing the efficiency of bonding. Additionally, Bianche et al. (2017) suggest that low-density timber demonstrates enhanced adhesive penetration compared to high-density timber, which exhibits limited permeability to adhesives.

Shear parallel to the grain at the glue line test

The shear strengths parallel to the fibres of the LSFC (glulam-CFRP) and LCFC (glulam only) specimens are presented in Table 1. At a moisture content of 12%, the LSFC exhibited a mean shear strength of 7.3 MPa, with a corresponding characteristic strength (f_{wk}) of 7.0 MPa. In contrast, the LCFC displayed a mean shear strength of 8.1 MPa, with a characteristic strength of 7.6 MPa.

Table 1: Shear strength parallel to the grain at the glue line in the glulam specimens without CFRP (LSFC) and with CFRP (LCFC).

Specimen	LSFC	LCFC
1	7.3	6.9
2	7.4	7.1
3	7.4	7.2
4	7.8	7.4
5	7.9	7.7
6	7.9	7.6
7	8.0	7.9
8	8.5	8.3
9	8.8	8.3
10	9.0	9.3
11	9.3	9.2
12	9.5	10.2
Mean	8.2	8.1
SD	0.8	1.0
CV (%)	9.3	12.4
f_{wk}	8.6	7.6

Note: SD = Standard deviation; CV = Coefficient of variation; f_{wk} = characteristic strength at 12% moisture content

A marginal percentage increase of 1.2% was observed in the average shear strength of LSFC (8.2 MPa) relative to the average shear strength of LCFC (8.1 MPa). However, this incremental difference lacks statistical significance, as indicated by the ANOVA analysis result: $F = 0.14$, which falls below the critical F value of 4.30.

Fracture of the specimens occurred exclusively within the timber region (Figure 6), indicating the sufficient bond strength offered by the polyurethane adhesive. According to Nadir et al. (2014), the occurrence of timber failure is commonly regarded as an indicative measure of the adhesive bond strength, signifying that the adhesive bonds exhibit superior strength in comparison to the timber itself.

a) Fracture line of the specimen without CFRP

b) Fracture line of the specimen with CFRP

Figure 6: Fractured specimens of the shear parallel to the grain at the glue line test

Azambuja (2006) conducted shear strength tests at the glue line using a polyurethane adhesive based on castor oil for *Eucalyptus grandis* timber. The obtained shear strength was 8.4 MPa for defect-free specimens, a value comparable to the shear resistances of LSFC (8.2 MPa) and LCFC (8.1 MPa). Nadir et al. (2014) investigated the adhesive/timber connection through shear force testing, finding a shear strength of 8.59 MPa for rubber wood (*Hevea brasiliensis*) bonded with PVA adhesive, with a timber failure percentage of 99.7%. Comparing these results, it can be observed that the average resistance of LSFC (8.2 MPa) closely aligns with the findings of the authors (8.59 MPa).

These obtained values are also consistent with those reported by Bianchi (2020), who obtained shear resistance ranging from 6 to 8 MPa using the same two-component polyurethane adhesive employed in this research. Additionally, Bianche et al. (2017) achieved shear strength of 7.6 MPa at the glue line with an adhesive quantity of 200 g/m² and 8.1 MPa with a quantity of 250 g/m². Nadir et al. (2016) conducted shear tests on samples bonded with PVA adhesive, considering a minimum adhesive strength of 5.4 MPa for glulam. Notably, the average shear strengths obtained in this study were higher (8.2 MPa for samples without reinforcement and 8.1 MPa for reinforced samples) than the minimum required adhesive strength.

Four-point bending test.

Table 2 presents the findings regarding the bending strength and modulus of elasticity of the LSFC specimens, characterized by a cross-sectional dimension of 4 cm x 4 cm. The mean bending strength was determined to be 71.9 MPa, while the mean modulus of elasticity was calculated as 12862 MPa based on the data obtained from six specimens.

Table 2: Results of four-point bending tests of glulam without CFRP (LSFC)

Specimen	MC (%)	f_m (Mpa)	E_0 (Mpa)
1	16.3	54.3	-
2	16.0	55.7	-
3	15.2	58.4	-
4	12.3	64.1	10330
5	10.1	64.1	11410
6	15.9	65.7	-
7	16.0	66.0	-
8	12.5	70.9	11652
9	10.5	81.0	16567
10	11.0	84.4	13104
11	10.7	94.5	14107
12	15.6	104.1	-
Mean	13.5	71.9	12862
SD	2.5	15.8	2250
CV (%)	18.7	21.9	18.0

Note: MC = moisture content; f_m = bending strength; E_0 = Modulus of elasticity; SD = Standard deviation; CV = Coefficient of variation.

Table 3 presents the results obtained from the four-point bending test conducted on the LCFC specimens (glulam-CFRP). The mean bending strength was determined to be 69.3 MPa, while the mean modulus of elasticity was determined as 12,854 MPa. Comparing the LCFC (69.3 MPa) with the LSFC (71.9 MPa), a reduction of 3.6% in bending strength was observed, while the difference in the modulus of elasticity was found to be less than 0.1%. Through the application of the ANOVA statistical test to analyze the two sample groups, no statistically significant difference was identified between the LSFC and the LCFC specimens. This conclusion is supported by the calculated F-value (0.26), which is below the F-critical (4.30), indicating the absence of a significant variation between the two groups.

Table 3: Results of four-point bending tests of glulam with CFRP (LSFC)

Specimen	MC (%)	f_m (Mpa)	E_0 (Mpa)
1	16.2	48.3	
2	15.1	64.1	13069
3	16.2	64.1	12831
4	15.0	67.6	-
5	15.6	70.0	-
6	15.0	70.9	11235
7	11.2	70.9	14033
8	14.7	72.4	-
9	16.3	74.3	13102
10	15.1	75.9	-
11	16.3	76.4	-
12	16.5	77.0	-
Mean	15.3	69.3	12854
SD	1.4	7.9	169
CV (%)	9.4	11.4	1.3

Note: MC = moisture content; f_m = bending strength; E_0 = Modulus of elasticity; SD = Standard deviation; CV = Coefficient of variation.

A linear relationship was found between the applied load and the displacement, indicating an elastic behaviour of the specimens. The failure of the specimens was primarily attributed to tension in the fibres in the bottom part of the cross-section, which aligns with findings reported by Brunetti et al. (2019). Their study highlighted a notable distinction in the behaviour of reinforced and unreinforced beams, with reinforced beams displaying non-linear phases indicative of ductile behaviour. It was argued that all glulam beams, regardless of reinforcement, exhibited predominantly linear elastic behaviour until failure, which typically initiated from defects or irregularities in the timber. The results of this study are consistent with these observations, supporting the existing understanding of glulam beam mechanical behaviour.

The load-displacement behaviour does not differentiate from LSFC to LCFC samples, since the location of the CFRP was not to reinforce the piece, but to assess whether the adhesive would be efficient.

Figure 7 illustrates the failure of the LCFC specimen, revealing the presence of a knot at the bottom of the sample where it is predominantly in tension, indicating the initiation of failure at the knot. Consequently, both LSFC and LCFC specimens exhibited a characteristic failure pattern characterised by pull-out failure at the bottom. In the presence of defects, failure initiation occurred at the knot locations.

Figure 7: Fracture line of LCFC specimen

The rupture phenomenon was observed to be localized away from the glue line interface. Khelifa et al. (2013) say that the presence of kinematic continuity between the adhesive and timber in bending elements reinforced with CFRP, a characteristic that was coherent with the observed failure pattern predominantly occurring within the timber itself.

Shear strength parallel to the grain

Table 4 exhibits the findings pertaining to the shear strength parallel to the grain of the glulam specimens, both those without CFRP reinforcement (LSFC) and those with CFRP reinforcement (LCFC). The average shear strength at a moisture content of 12% for LSFC was determined to be 6.9 MPa, whereas for LCFC, it was found to be 6.1 MPa.

Table 4: Shear strength parallel to the grain of the glulam specimens without CFRP (LSFC) and CFRP (LCFC)

Specimen	LSFC	LCFC
1	7.6	5.9
2	6.9	6.0
3	6.6	5.9
4	5.9	5.8
5	5.8	5.9
6	6.9	6.3
7	8.5	5.3
8	6.1	6.0
9	6.0	6.2
10	7.2	6.4
11	7.6	6.6
12	7.9	6.7
Mean	6.9	6.1
SD	0.9	0.4
CV (%)	13.0	6.3

Note: SD = Standard deviation; CV = Coefficient of variation.

In relation to the LSFC samples (6.9 MPa), a reduction of 11.6% was observed, representing a statistically significant difference ($F > F_{critical}$). Nevertheless, the typical fracture pattern observed in LCFC specimens was similar to that of LSFC specimens, occurring outside the glue line (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Typical failure in shear

Figure 8 shows the typical failure pattern observed in the specimens, specifically in the fibres of the bottom located in the central part of the specimen. This type of failure, as described by Matos and Molina (2016), indicates that the wood does not fully utilise its shear resistance capacity. Additionally, the authors mentioned that this form of rupture was predominant for Eucalyptus timber.

CONCLUSIONS

Considering the results obtained through the experimental program, it was possible to conclude that:

- the basic density of *Eucalyptus urophylla* clone COP 1404 is within the recommended density range for glulam production;
- the timber showed adequate dimensional stability, proving to be a good option to be used in construction. Furthermore, the dimensional distortions were within acceptable parameters, showing good stability of the timber in relation to splitting and twisting;

- the polyurethane adhesive based on castor beans oil was efficient as an adhesive for glulam produced with clone COP 1404 timber (LSFC). A fact also occurred for the LCFC, which also had its rupture in the wood, in the shear test on the glue sheet;
- the shear test parallel to the fibres carried out according to NBR 7190-4 for the LSFC and the LCFC indicated the behaviour of a single specimen, whose rupture was characterised by tension of the bottom edge fibres in the middle span of the specimen;
- the polyurethane adhesive proved to be efficient as adhesive of the clonal species COP 1404 and carbon fibre.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.